

Guidelines for publications within NFFA-Europe

Introduction

Here is a list of practical actions to publish the results of the research activity within the NFFA-Europe Pilot project. These guidelines summarise the requirements included in the NFFA-Europe Pilot Grant Agreement, in the [NFFA-Europe User Declaration Agreement](#), in the [NFFA-Europe Research Data Policy](#) and in the [NFFA-Europe Data Management Plan](#).

The Glossary of terms used in this document can be found [HERE](#).

For any question related to Open Access to Scientific Publications and to Research Data write to u.serdissemination@nffa.eu.

Scientific Publications

Definition: A Scientific Publication is any of the following contributions (peer-reviewed or not): article in a scientific journal, monograph, book or book chapter, conference proceedings and ‘grey literature’ (i.e. informally published material not having gone through a standard publishing process, e.g. reports, highlights).

If researchers affiliated with a NFFA-Europe Pilot Beneficiary are within the authors of a peer-reviewed Scientific Publication resulting from a research work within NFFA-Europe, ***it is mandatory*** to deposit in a trusted repository and to provide Open Access (free of charge online access) either to the published version or accepted peer-reviewed version of the article within six months of publication. *All 7 steps listed below are mandatory.*

In all other cases, Research Users are ***encouraged*** to choose Open Access for their Scientific Publications. *Only steps 1 and 2 listed below are mandatory.*

Steps

1. **Acknowledge** the project in your Scientific Publication including:
 - if applicable, the following sentence: “*This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007417, having benefited from the access provided by [access provider Institution] in [access site] within the framework of the NFFA-Europe Pilot Transnational Access Activity, proposal [IDXXXX].*”;
 - otherwise, the following sentence: “*This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, under grant agreement No 101007417 NFFA-Europe Pilot*”;
 - the NFFA-Europe Pilot staff members who ensured the access support;
 - [the EU emblem](#).

2. **Communicate** at least tentative title, list of authors, abstract and name of the repository where you intend to publish the related Research Data at least 20 days before any submission to publication, writing to userdissemination@nffa.eu and, if the Scientific Publication results from a NFFA-Europe *Joint Activity*, also to science@nffa.eu, specifying the JA number.

3. **Submit** your article to a journal whose policies are in line with open access requirements. You can choose between:
 - an Open Access journal (Gold Open Access);
You can look for an Open Access journal on the DOAJ website or publish on Open Research Europe, the open access platform of the European Commission. You may be required to pay an Article Processing Charge (APC) to support the costs of the publication process and peer-review. In case one of the authors is affiliated with a NFFA-Europe Pilot Beneficiary, the cost can be borne by NFFA-Europe.
 - a traditional subscription scientific journal that allows you to deposit a copy of your article in an online repository and provide open access to it after a maximum of 6 months (Green Open Access);
You can check the conditions of scientific journals through Sherpa Romeo. In case of a longer embargo, you have to choose a different journal or negotiate with the editor for a shorter embargo. In the latter case, you can use this addendum template.
 - a traditional subscription scientific journal that allows you to make your article open access by paying a fee (Hybrid Open Access).
Check if the institution you are affiliated with has entered into transformative agreements or read and publish agreements with the journal of your choice before proceeding to sign the Journal Publishing Agreement with the publisher. Otherwise, in case one of the authors is affiliated with a NFFA-Europe Pilot Beneficiary, the cost can be borne by NFFA-Europe. Try to avoid double-dipping.

4. **Choose** the [appropriate online repository](#) for scientific publications to upload your work, remembering that it has to be compliant with the journal policy and with OpenAIRE requirements. It can be an institutional repository, a discipline-specific repository or a multipurpose repository like [Zenodo](#).

5. **Deposit** either the published version or accepted version (*postprint*) of your article in the chosen repository (check the publisher's policy through [Sherpa Romeo](#) to determine which version you can upload). This is mandatory also in case of Gold and Hybrid open access. Always assign to the deposition the same DOI as the original article, or at least cite it in the related identifiers.

6. **Identify** the deposited publication by indicating in the repository at least the following descriptive metadata:
 - DOI of the original article
 - Funding: “Horizon 2020”
 - Grant project name, acronym and number: "Nanoscience Foundries and Fine Analysis - Europe|PILOT, NEP, 101007417"
 - Proposal ID number (if applicable)
 - Date of publication and duration of the embargo period (if applicable)
 - Related identifiers: DOI of the associated Research Data and other research outputs (if applicable).

7. **Ensure open access to the deposited publication** — via the repository. Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) is recommended. Open Access must be ensured within six months of the publication date.

Publication Data

Definition: Publication Data are datasets generated in the NFFA-Europe PILOT project needed to validate the Results presented in a Scientific Publication or appearing in it. Publication Data include Raw Data, Analysed Data and all the relevant Metadata on Measurement and Data Analysis to validate them.

It is mandatory to deposit in a trusted repository and to provide Open access (free of charge online access) to any Research Data and associated metadata needed to validate **any** Scientific Publication resulting from a research work within NFFA-Europe, for both Research Users and researchers affiliated with a NFFA-Europe PILOT Beneficiary or Third Party.

All 7 steps listed below are mandatory.

Steps

1. **Collect** all Publication Data generated in the project related to your Scientific Publication.

The Publication Data related to a Dataset (spectrum or image) appearing in a Scientific Publication includes:

- *the file of the data as it appears in the Scientific Publication;*
- *the respective Raw Data file, if Data Analysis has been performed;*
- *the related Metadata, as described in pt. 2, either included in the data files or in a separated file.*

2. **Collect** and organise all Metadata related to Publication Data, if available, according to a Metadata Standard for the related Measurement Technique. Metadata must include all the information necessary to validate or re-use the data.

- *Metadata must include:*
 - *information on the Data Analysis performed to get from Raw Data to the published data - if applicable (e.g. the log(s) of the Data Analysis Software)*
 - *information on the Data Analysis Software and any other tool needed to re-use or validate the data (e.g. specialised software or software code, algorithms and analysis protocols).*
- *Metadata should also include:*
 - *information on the Sample and the Sample Preparation procedure - if applicable (e.g. an extract of the logbook with the parameters of the preparation)*
 - *information on the Instrument settings related to the generated data (e.g. those usually accompanying the Raw Data file)*

An overview of existing Metadata Standards organised by discipline can be found on the [Research Data Alliance's Metadata Standards Directory](#), on the [Digital Curation Center website](#) or on [FAIRsharing.org](#). NFFA-Europe recommends using [NeXus](#) format. Where no appropriate and formal Metadata Standard exists, writing "readme" style metadata file and linking it to the data is an appropriate strategy. In any case, all the Metadata has to be clearly identifiable and easily related to its specific data file.

3. **Convert**, if needed, the Publication Data to a file format that can be opened with an open-source (or at least free) multi-platform software and make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate it — free of charge.

Examples:

- *data and Metadata are saved into NeXus/HDF5 file format;*
- *data and Metadata are saved in (separated or joint) text files;*
- *data is saved in common image format such as PNG or TIFF (in the latter case lossless compression has to be used in order to avoid data loss) and Metadata is saved in text files.*

4. **Choose** the [appropriate online repository](#) to upload your data, remembering it has to be compatible with OpenAIRE and capable of assigning a Persistent Identifier (PID) - such as a DOI.

Search for a discipline-specific Data Repository ([compatible with OpenAIRE](#)) or use the multidisciplinary open repository [Zenodo](#).

5. **Deposit** the Publication Data in the chosen Data repository; provide - where possible - the tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data (e.g. specialised software or software code, algorithms and analysis protocols) - via the Data Repository or by other means. Do not assign to the dataset deposition the same DOI as the article, always create a new identifier.

Example: Any NeXus/HDF5 file, or compressed archive containing the Publication Data as defined above, can be deposited on Zenodo (also in closed or embargoed access) at any time before publication (e.g. throughout the data acquisition or analysis process).

6. **Identify** the deposited data by indicating in the Data Repository at least the following descriptive metadata:

- Brief description, Date of deposit and Author(s) of the Dataset
- Funding: "Horizon 2020"
- Grant project name, acronym and number: "Nanoscience Foundries and Fine Analysis - Europe|PILOT, NEP, 101007417"
- Proposal ID number (if applicable)
- Related identifiers: DOI of the related Scientific Publication(s) and other research outputs (if applicable)

7. **Ensure Open Access to the deposited data** — via the Data Repository — under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or licences with equivalent rights.

Open Access to the data must be ensured at the latest on the publication date of the related Scientific Publication.

Example: The Publication Data, previously deposited on Zenodo in closed or embargoed access, is edited and set Open Access rights. When changing to Open Access, the licence "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International" is specified.